

**make
a
thek**

Deliverable D9.1 CDO Plan & Assets

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Revision of History

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List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Description
BFW	Berlin Fashion Week
CCI	Cultural and Creative Industries
CDO	Communication, Dissemination and Outreach
CH	Cultural Heritage
CCS	Creative and Cultural Sector
CP	Consortium Partners
DDP	Distributed Design Platform
ECA	European Crafts Alliance
FCF	Sihtasutus Fab City Foundation
FRG	Fashion Revolution Germany
FRW	Fashion Revolution Week
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GIG	Global Innovation Gathering e.V.
IAAC	Institut d'Arquitectura Avançada de Catalunya
NEB	New European Bauhaus Festival
OD	OpenDot SRL
OER	Open Educational Resources
PL2030	Public Libraries 2030
SEO	Search Engine Optimization
UMA	Ukrainian Makers Association
UX/UI	User Experience / User Interface
WCEF	World Circular Economy Forum
WP	Work Package
WP 3	Mapping and Community Activation
WP 5	Capacity Development

WP 6	Community Engagement
WP 7	European Public Library Pilots
WP 8	Exploitation and Sustainability
WP 9	CDO1 (Communication, Dissemination & Outreach 1)
WP 10	CDO2 (Communication, Dissemination & Outreach 2)
ZSI	Zentrum für Soziale Innovation GmbH

1. Introduction

1.1 make-a-thek Project Summary

make-a-thek aims to establish modular, replicable makerspace set-ups within public libraries, offering open access to innovative and circular approaches in fashion and crafts. Grounded in extensive mapping and participatory co-creation, the project will develop a comprehensive resource toolkit and a suite of open educational resources (OERs) tailored for fashion and craft-focused makerspaces in libraries. These will be piloted in at least nine European and three international library locations.

Throughout these pilot trials, communities of practitioners and prosumers¹ (engaged citizens) will co-design and test new models for integrating traditional heritage crafts with digital fabrication techniques. This process will foster the exchange and development of tools, skills, techniques, and cultural practices that promote circularity in fashion and crafts.

Aligned with the principles of the New European Bauhaus², make-a-thek embodies:

- Inclusivity: by democratising access to innovation technologies and creating new public infrastructures that invite citizens to actively participate in the green transition,
- Sustainability: by empowering communities to contribute to a circular society through creative and practical engagement,

¹ **Prosumer** (a portmanteau of *producer* and *consumer*) refers to individuals who are actively involved in the creation, adaptation, repair or improvement of the products or services they use.

² <https://new-european-bauhaus.europa.eu/>

- Enrichment: by enabling personal and collective expression through hands-on work in fashion and crafts.

With a strong focus on social innovation, the project aims to generate impact across four key dimensions, measured through Societal Readiness Levels and aligned with the European Commission's work programme:

- Empowering New Prosumers in Fashion and Crafts
- Positioning Public Libraries as Inclusive Hubs for Circular Knowledge and Creation
- Preserving Heritage Crafts through Digital Innovation and Skills Development
- Fostering Circularity and Green Innovation in Fashion and Craft Sectors

To ensure sustainability and long-term uptake, make-a-thek will pursue a scaling strategy that extends beyond the pilot sites. This includes building a broader network, embedding practices into existing infrastructures, and producing an make-a-thek (Scaling) Guide targeted at Cultural and Creative Sectors as well as Cultural Heritage stakeholders.

1.2 Deliverable Executive Summary

This Communication, Dissemination & Outreach (CDO) strategy outlines how make-a-thek will be communicated with target audiences and stakeholders to meet established communication and project goals.

A core element of the CDO is the make-a-thek communication implementation plan that will be regularly reviewed and updated in WP9 and WP10.

The CDO's specific goal is to ensure that the planned makerspace concepts in the selected libraries come to life as vibrant, well-frequented spaces that invite active participation. The aim is to make the make-a-thek makerspaces lively, engaging, and widely used by diverse audiences. The project will also be communicated to various stakeholders, policymakers, and the general public. Achieving this requires carefully targeted communication across the most effective channels to reach, inspire, and mobilize local communities.

In addition to the pilot libraries where make-a-thek makerspaces will pilot, a mobile makerspace in the form of a bus will tour across Europe. This bus will also be accompanied by visual, audio, and/or media content. The detailed communication concept for the CDO activities around the bus will be developed once the involved work packages enter the detailed planning phase for the mobile makerspace.

make-a-thek's strategy will focus on three key areas:

Communication – Promoting the project and its core themes to raise awareness and encourage engagement across diverse audiences

Dissemination – Sharing information about the project's outcomes and related innovations to foster understanding and acceptance among stakeholders.

Outreach – Ensuring that project results are made publicly accessible to support their adoption by individuals and organizations beyond the project's immediate scope.

To achieve its goals, make-a-thek's communication, dissemination, and outreach (CDO) strategy relies on a participatory, bottom-up approach and utilizes a wide range of media and press channels. It ensures that results are shared not only within the project but also widely beyond, supporting long-term impact. The project will make use of the consortium's existing communication channels, networks, and communities—particularly those in crafts, fashion, libraries, and makerspaces—to spread and amplify its results.

A strong visual identity and clear, inclusive messaging—using accessible language, icons, and templates—will guide all communication and marketing. A user-friendly Open Source Communications Toolkit will provide practical materials such as branding assets, adaptable templates, social media and event guidelines, and instructions for creating tactile materials. This toolkit will help partners and participants share the project effectively in different languages and contexts.

A communications campaign will invite diverse voices from society to engage with the project. The project website will serve as a central platform for sharing outputs, showcasing achievements, and supporting long-term access to resources. Content such as infographics, videos, and blog posts will follow easy-to-use design principles to inspire broader engagement.

Social media, email campaigns, and regional mailing lists will connect with target groups, while media outreach will help secure local, regional, and thematic coverage. Influencers and multipliers events from partner networks will activate communities around events and pilots.

All public deliverables and results will be made available under Creative Commons licenses, hosted in open-access repositories. The strategy also aims to reach underrepresented communities, contribute to policy dialogue, and support new initiatives.

Finally, the success of the CDO strategy will be continuously measured using predefined indicators and participant feedback, ensuring the approach remains relevant and impactful throughout—and beyond—the project's lifetime.

FRG is responsible for project CDO however many of the targets and goals are shared across all consortium partners.

2. Objectives and Approach

The CDO strategy for make-a-thek focuses on building awareness, fostering engagement, and supporting long-term impact through the following key goals:

- **Raise awareness & interest in make-a-thek.**
Raising awareness in local communities about circularity in fashion and crafts.
- **Encourage participation in make-a-thek events and the pilots.**
Engaging local communities, circularity experts, makers, craftspeople and the fashion industry to co-create solutions to test local circular economy products and services in fashion and crafts.
- **Ensuring access to make-a-thek KIT & OER & Comms toolkit.**
Enabling pilot libraries and project partners to communicate make-a-thek easily with a consistent voice by providing brand resources, tools and templates. Provide easy access to make-a-thek KIT & OER.
- **Invite people, esp. from underrepresented groups, to engage with their local library's make-a-thek.**
- **Support successful implementation of pilots and roll out of project results.**
Supporting positioning public libraries as hubs and maker spaces for circular knowledge and co-creation
- **Build relationships & establish interest in make-a-thek's policy recommendations.**
Point out the importance of makerspaces in public libraries for a for circular society and for social inclusion and cohesion
- **Creating a long-term communication plan.**
Developing a strategy that effectively communicates the project's results to relevant stakeholders, highlighting the benefits for building a circular society and fostering social inclusion and community cohesion—while motivating long-term use of the materials and tools.

2.1 Target Audience

Understanding who make-a-thek is trying to reach is essential for tailoring communication and dissemination efforts to suit each group's specific needs and interests. This approach focuses on crafting and delivering messages that resonate by analyzing the characteristics of each audience and selecting the most effective ways to engage them.

Relevant stakeholders and target groups were mapped out during the proposal stage of the project:

- General public
- Local audiences, incl. prosumers
- Fashion people
- Policy makers
- Librarians
- Makers
- Crafts-people
- Circularity experts
- Underrecognised communities, particularly youth³, but also older adults, migrants

During the first consortium meeting in February 2025, the consortium partners (CP) classified these target groups in a co-creative workshop, according to their relevance in the networks of the CP's organisations in order to better understand and reach each target group.

³ "For statistical purposes, the United Nations, without prejudice to any other definitions made by Member States, defines 'youth' as those persons between the ages of 15 and 24 years." – United Nations <https://www.un.org/en/global-issues/youth>

Figure 01: Example of developing target groups in the co-creation process using the Miro tool from the consortium meeting in February 2025

make-a-thek engages diverse audiences with tailored communication goals to maximize relevance and impact. The strategy supports public awareness and pilot participation, while providing tools and resources to professionals. Target groups include general audiences, local communities, librarians, fashion and craft practitioners, makers, circularity experts, and policymakers. Special focus is placed on inclusivity—reaching underrepresented groups like youth—and highlighting public libraries as hubs for innovation, sustainability, and cultural heritage within the circular economy. The following sections outline the specific target groups, their unique needs, and how the project addresses each to foster awareness, participation, and collaboration.

The following table shows which tools and channels will be used to engage each target group.

Table 01: Target groups with goals and tools

Target Groups	Main Goal	Tool/Channel
General public	Raise awareness of make-a-thek’s mission and results, encourage participation in events and pilots, focusing on crafts, fashion, and a circular society.	Social media campaign using channels of all consortium members. National & international press. Influencers from the consortium’s communities.
Local audiences, incl. prosumers:	Invite people, especially from underrepresented groups, to engage with their local make-a-thek,	Social media channels of all consortium members with more individual messaging addressing regional & local

	encouraging participation in activities and pilots, with a focus on circular society, upcycling, recycling, repair, sustainable business models, and consumption.	communities. Targeted PR with focus on regional press, specialised press (craft, circularity, design, innovation, fashion, heritage, library, maker, tech), invitations to events. Local and international meet-ups. Pilot events in public libraries. (with WP 3,6,7,8) ⁴
Librarians	Promote make-a-thek, support pilot implementation and access to KIT and OER, highlighting makerspaces in public libraries as drivers of circular society and innovation in Cultural Heritage and the Creative and Cultural Sector.	Targeted social media campaigns from a librarian's perspective, customised PR for library-focused media and influencers, local and international meet-ups, knowledge-sharing events, and pilot activities in public libraries. (with WP 3,5,6,7,8) ⁵
Fashion people	Encourage participation in make-a-thek activities and pilots, ensure access to KIT and OER, focusing on circularity in fashion and crafts, digital and maker innovation, and cultural heritage preservation.	Targeted social media campaigns and customised PR focused on fashion media and influencers, complemented by local and international meet-ups, knowledge-sharing events, and pilot activities in public libraries. (with WP 3,5,6,7,8)
Policy makers	Building relationships & establishing interest in make-a-thek's policy recommendations. Addressing: CHs role in circularity for CCIs, digital & maker innovation, and importance of makerspaces in public libraries for a circular society.	Targeted social media engagement with policymakers on make-a-thek goals, direct outreach via email or invitations to pilot events in public libraries, and city-level dialogues on policy recommendations and project insights. (with WP 7, WP8)
Makers	Promote participation in make-a-thek pilots, ensure KIT and OER access, highlighting makers' role in circular society and libraries as key partners.	Targeted social media campaigns and customised PR focusing on maker-related media and influencers, alongside local and international meet-ups, knowledge-sharing

⁴ building also on results from other WP 3, WP 6, WP 7, WP 8

⁵ building also on results from other WP 3, WP 5, WP 6, WP 7, WP 8

		events, and pilot activities held in public libraries. (with WP 3,5,6,7,8).
Crafts People	Encourage participation in make-a-thek pilots, ensure KIT and OER access, emphasizing crafts in circular society, maker and digital tech, fashion, and libraries' role in cultural innovation.	Targeted social media and customised PR focused on craft media and influencers, along with local and international meet-ups, knowledge-sharing events, and pilot activities in public libraries. (with WP 3,5,6,7,8).
Circularity experts	Encourage participation in make-a-thek pilots, ensure KIT and OER access, focusing on circularity in crafts and fashion, innovative digital and maker approaches, and their relevance for CCI and CH preservation.	Targeted social media and customised PR focused on circularity media and influencers, combined with local and international meet-ups, knowledge-sharing events, and pilot activities in public libraries. (with WP 3,5,6,7,8).
Underrecognised communities/ particularly young people	Encourage participation in make-a-thek pilots to foster social & digital innovation and cultural heritage preservation	Targeted social media in selected channels (e.g. TikTok) with focus on local communities with focus on fashion, crafts, making (e.g. knitting, crochet) (with WP 3,5,6,7,8).

2.2 Channels and Actions

make-a-thek will utilise both online and offline channels to execute the CDO strategy. Each channel is tailored to effectively engage the target audiences. An overview is provided below.

2.2.1 Online Channels

Table 02: Online Channels

Channel	Purpose	Frequency
Website	Central hub with project information, resources, links to social media channels & newsletter signup.	Update every month (e.g. list of events or changes in the project).

Newsletter	Share updates, progress, and other news about the project.	Quarterly.
Instagram	Sharing project updates & invites, recaps from events, multimedia. Community management.	Every 1-3 days, in accordance with the project's progress and activities.
Linkedin	Share outputs, invites and updates.	Approx. once a week in accordance with the project's progress and activities
Facebook	Share outputs, invites and updates. Especially in year 2 during the pilot makerspaces we will use Facebook groups to invite targeted communities.	In accordance with the project's progress and activities.
Press	Starting around earth overshoot day in August 2025, regular press releases will be sent digitally to a distribution list, on an international level. Communication campaign milestones are set in advance to plan the press releases (see timeline in 5.3).	In accordance with the project's progress and activities.
Email Signature	Email signature template for (Consortium partners) CP to promote the project in email correspondence.	
YouTube	Documentation and collection of video content, especially supporting materials from the mobile makerspace (bus).	Will start between month 7 and 12

2.2.2 Offline Channels

Table 03: Offline Channels

Channel	Purpose	Frequency
Branding & identity	Logo, style guide, and standardized project presentation materials (including Google Sheets for deliverables, Google Slides, Canva presentations, Canva templates for social media, press releases, and related assets) ensures clear, inclusive, and professional	The first version is available in April 2025. At month 6, the beta version of the comms toolkit will be replaced by the open source final version comms toolkit. This version will be updated and adapted as

	communication across all channels— text, visuals, and tone.	required during the course of the project.
Merch material (Posters, flyers, sewing sets, bookmarks, banners with general project information, best practices and how-to information for events.)	Raise awareness and engagement by providing general project information, best practices, and how-to guidance for events in a visually appealing and hands-on format.	Will be finalised at the end of July 2025 and updated as required.
Events & workshops	Partners should promote make-a-thek at events, use the right branding, and report to FRG.	

2.3 Strategic Approach

Communication will take place at hyper-local, European, and international levels.

FRG, as the WP leader, will coordinate the communication campaign at the European and international level, with consortium partners (CP), pilot libraries and target audiences. At a local level, regional partners and local pilot libraries will be empowered to manage local community communication to raise awareness and increase engagement with their make-a-thek pilot.

We will achieve this by:

- Setting up a communication campaign and dividing it into distinct phases.
- Having a central, detailed communication implementation plan for transparency and accountability.
- Managing media, association and political communication for big milestone events.
- Providing communication resources on the make-a-thek website for stakeholders and pilot libraries to promote to their own communities.
- Offering webinars to the pilot libraries on how to use the communication resources, best practices and knowledge sharing.

- Maintaining regular communication with all relevant stakeholders (meetings and newsletters), encouraging feedback and creating new resources based on their needs.
- Using easy language and translation tools as well as involving local native speakers.

The following table provides a clear overview of the tools and tactics.

Table 04: Communication tools and tactics

Tool/Channel	Tactic 1	Tactic 2	Tactic 3
<u>Events</u>	public events	internal events	online events
<u>Website</u>	public information including events, about info, press resources	project partner resources	Feedback form
<u>Public relations</u>	Social media: Instagram, LinkedIn	Quarterly newsletter	International/ regional press releases
<u>Resources for project partners & libraries</u>	Communications toolkit	Event toolkit	
<u>Communication webinars</u>	Online webinars with local libraries to support them with PR, communication, event best practice and knowledge share.		
<u>White label content⁶</u>	Regularly provide content to all partners to share through their network		
<u>Communication Campaign Plan</u>	spreadsheet open to all project partners to guarantee an overview on planned communication campaign	Social Media plan is included in the comms plan	tracking list of events & shared content is linked to the comms plan

⁶ **White label content** means that one partner (FRG) develops content—like press release, social media assets or texts for newsletters—that the other CP can adapt, rebrand, and use as their own within their countries or networks.

2.4 Communication Principles

These principles guide our decisions about communication and how we communicate.

Accessible – Our communication is clear and easy to understand. We strive to make our information accessible to a wide range of people, acknowledging that full accessibility for everyone, including those with visual, hearing, or cognitive disabilities, may not always be achievable. Nevertheless, we are committed to continuously improving access.

Transparent – We are as transparent as possible about what is possible, what we commit to, what we share.

Inclusive – We use inclusive language. We create a sense of belonging where everyone is welcome.

Consistent – We communicate regularly and consistently. We try to avoid surprises.

2.5 Risks and Mitigation

Table 05: Communication risks and how we mitigate them

Communication risks to make-a-thek	How we will mitigate them
Many different countries with different languages, cultures, target audiences	Use clear, accessible language (included in tone of voice). Project partner to adapt messages to their target audiences.
Local public libraries may not have enough capacity or communication skills to effectively promote their programmes.	Communication kit to include a customisable pitch deck so public libraries can get local funding and support. Include call to action in media release templates. Check in with public libraries to support.
Political environment	Harmonized messages and positions by the CP. Focus on concrete advantages and needs of the projects approach.

3. Key Channels and Activities

3.1 Website

The project website serves a dual purpose: it functions both as a central hub for communication and as a platform for sharing project results. Deliverables will be published through <https://zenodo.org/communities/make-a-thek> and linked to makeathek.eu. The website's primary aim is to guide stakeholders and participants toward relevant information and resources, enhancing both the visibility of the project and the long-term impact of its outcomes. Managed and monitored by FRG, the website will be regularly updated with news, events, and project outputs. After the project ends in January 2028, FRG will integrate makeathek.eu into its own homepage, while existing links will remain active or be redirected accordingly. All resources will remain accessible for at least three more years.

To support this, project partners will be expected to contribute content for social media posts, supply information for the events calendar, and share deliverables and other outputs for timely publication.

Additionally, the website will be integrated with other digital platforms (e.g. [A-gain guide](#), [craft atlas](#)) associated with the project.

The website layout and design are described in section 6.2.1.

3.2 Social Media

make-a-thek will maintain active accounts on Instagram, LinkedIn, and Facebook, each aligned with the project's visual identity and branding. These social media channels will be strategically managed by FRG to ensure consistent and effective messaging.

Project partners are expected to contribute to the outreach by sharing, reposting, and interacting with make-a-thek content. All posts should tag the official project accounts and include the designated make-a-thek hashtag to enhance visibility and coherence across platforms.

In line with the Horizon Europe Model Grant Agreement, all social media posts related to the project also include the hashtags #HorizonEU, #EUInnovation, #ResearchImpactEU and #NewEuropeanBauhaus. Additional recommendations and best practices can be found in the Communication, Dissemination & Exploitation guide provided by the European Commission.

3.3 Newsletter & Press

A newsletter via the Mailchimp platform will be sent approximately every three months to share news, updates, and information about the current status of the project. The recipients include the general public or specific audiences interested in the project or topics such as circularity, fashion, crafts, makerspaces, libraries, EU Horizon projects, social innovation, and the CCI. Important links to the make-a-thek website, social media channels, and the event calendar will also be included in the newsletter.

Starting from August 2025, around Earth Overshoot Day, FRG will regularly send press releases through an international professional media distribution list to present the project, share news, and invite to related events. In addition to this international distribution, project partners are encouraged to forward these press releases within their local networks, such as through their own press lists, newsletters, or community networks.

3.4 Communication Campaign and Toolkit, Events Toolkit

FRG will prepare a Communications Toolkit with materials to promote make-a-thek, aligned with the project's brand guidelines. Partners requiring support for developing additional tailored materials for specific activities or events should notify FRG well in advance. Such requests will be reviewed and addressed by FRG on a case-by-case basis. Each partner remains responsible for producing their own deliverables and academic dissemination outputs, using the templates provided by FRG.

The Communications Toolkit also includes an Event Toolkit, which provides guidance on how to manage event communications, outlines the available printable materials, and offers recommendations for media coverage of the event.

3.5 Events

Consortium partners are expected to organise and participate in relevant sector events, including conferences, workshops, and fairs. They should actively seek opportunities to present and promote make-a-thek within their respective countries, as well as at both local and European levels. All partners are encouraged to represent the project at such events.

Whenever make-a-thek is presented, the responsible partner must report the event details to FRG. Proper use of the project logo and official naming is mandatory in all communication materials and presentations.

Key Events

Key events will help make-a-thek raise awareness, spark interest, and build ownership around its outputs. These events will support community engagement, knowledge sharing, and co-creation across the fashion, craft, and tech sectors. The project will conclude with a hybrid event and mobile exhibition, showcasing its impact and outcomes, potentially at the New European Bauhaus (NEB) Festival. Established networks and events will be used to reach citizens and stakeholders effectively.

More details on dissemination and events under 6.4.

4. Branding & Identity

4.1 Logo and Visual Identity

The development of a strong visual identity for the project, including the website and social media, is designed to clearly convey make-a-thek's key objectives and core values, ensuring easy recognition and meaningful connection with the target audience and stakeholders.

In a co-creative process from the very beginning, the visual language of the brand identity was developed. The logo and visual elements are designed to clearly reflect the participatory nature of the project and invite active involvement. The diverse audiences are meant to be inspired to engage through a logo and imagery that appeal broadly. The colors and visual identity enhance the enthusiasm for participation, networking, and learning. The core themes of fashion, heritage crafts, makers, libraries, and circularity are central and should be effectively represented through the visual elements.

The recognizability and modularity of the logo and the entire brand identity were key focuses during development. A clear goal from the start was to appeal to younger target audiences as well.

4.1.1 The Name

make-a-thek – make-a-thek is a proper noun and is always written in lowercase, whether at the beginning or in the middle of a sentence. Always write make-a-thek with hyphens.

mat – When using the acronym mat, make sure you put this in brackets first. Example: make-a-thek (mat).

4.1.2 The Logo

The logo was developed with the brand's core values in mind, aiming to establish a strong and authentic brand identity. It reflects key themes such as fashion, heritage crafts, public libraries, circularity, the circular economy, and social innovation. The mobile makerspace—specifically the bus and its planned route through Europe—played an important role in shaping the visual concept of the logo.

The creation process was co-creative in nature. Consortium partners were actively involved and provided input during the first three months via feedback forms and surveys. Fashion Revolution Germany led the process by sharing initial logo proposals, conducting surveys, and ultimately developing a visual language that laid the foundation for the final design.

The logo is designed to spark interest and participation. It is meant to be memorable, visually appealing, and dynamic—capturing the spirit of the project while resonating with diverse audiences and inspiring curiosity and engagement.

The make-a-thek logo is available in different versions. The main logo should always be the first choice. The mat icon is used when the main logo is no longer legible at smaller scales.

Figure 02: make-a-thek logo and icon

To keep it modular, additional colour versions of the logo and icon can be used. The contrast to the background must be clear to ensure good legibility. Further details on the correct and consistent application of the logo can be found in the style guide included in the Communications Toolkit.

Figure 03: make-a-thek logo variations - extract from styleguide pdf

4.2 Visual Elements

In addition to the logo, the visual elements that shape the brand identity of make-a-thek include a carefully defined color palette, gradients, and a range of graphic components. These comprise geometric and organic shapes, as well as illustrations and icons that can function like pictograms or serve as supportive visual storytelling tools. All these elements are clearly outlined in the style guide and are available in the Communications Toolkit under "Resources" to ensure consistent and effective use across all platforms and materials.

Figure 04: make-a-thek colour palette - extract from style guide pdf

Figure 05: make-a-thek icons - extract from style guide pdf

Figure 06: example of a visual background using the make-a-thek style guide

4.3 Style Guide

The style guide is a PDF document that provides clear instructions on how to implement and maintain the brand's communication strategy. It includes communication guidelines, an introduction to the brand's tone of voice, its vision and mission, and the core concept behind make-a-thek. It also offers a brief overview of the various communication channels used.

The second part of the style guide focuses on visual guidelines. It outlines the visual components of the brand and explains how to apply them consistently. This includes logo typography, the brand typeface, the defined color palette, and graphic elements. Together, these guidelines ensure a cohesive and recognizable visual identity.

The style guide is an integral part of the Communications Toolkit and serves as a practical resource for anyone working with the brand.

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Figure 07: Table of Contents from the Style Guide

4.4 Tone of Voice

make-a-thek uses clear, concrete language because it is an inclusive brand that is active both locally and internationally. Although it is a fun brand, we don't play with meaning. We make it easy to understand.

Sentences are short and easily translatable. We use modern, clean headings. Body text is just the right length to say what it needs to say.

The colourful, creative and artistic part of the brand is expressed through inspiring visuals and activating content formats.

We base our communication on the values of the New European Bauhaus: inclusive, sustainable and beautiful.

Figure 08: Co-creation session Feb 2025 “Tone of Voice” for make-a-thek

4.5 Core Story

In a disconnected world of fast fashion and throw-away things, make-a-thek brings back creativity, craftship and community. By partnering with selected libraries in Europe and beyond, make-a-thek gives a place for innovation, individuality, learning and sharing, promoting a more circular, local economy.

It brings together the great work that is already happening; strengthens public libraries as community hubs, and gives an international platform for the community circular movement.

We encourage people to move away from the consumerist model of design, use and waste - towards consciously thinking about what they buy, make, and use in fashion and crafts. At the same time we also inspire new circular business models

by co-creating the needed infrastructure for local production, care, repair and reuse or recycling. This allows for locally meaningful circular products and services to be trialled in a real-life setting.

make-a-thek pilots at selected public libraries and will be launched in early 2026. We are committed to transparency about our project. We will share our open source framework and resources so others can learn.

make-a-thek is funded by the European Union through its Horizon Europe programme for research and innovation. make-a-thek will run until January 2028.

4.6 Vision and Mission statement

Vision – make-a-thek envisions public libraries as a place for circular economy experience and co-creation focused on fashion and crafts.

Mission – make-a-thek pilots a scalable co-creation model with selected European and international libraries, building on existing community networks and initiatives.

4.7 Inclusive Communication

make-a-thek will place a strong emphasis on barrier-free and inclusive communication. This commitment includes:

- Prioritizing the use of gender-inclusive and diverse language
- Selecting images that reflect cultural and gender diversity
- Implementing accessible communication design, including content structure, appropriate font sizes, alternative text, and subtitles where feasible
- Using clear, straightforward language that avoids jargon and complex phrasing

5. Key Messages

Clear and targeted key messages are crucial for effective communication with different audiences. They help ensure that the project's purpose, goals, and benefits are easily understood and resonate with each group's interests and needs. By tailoring messages appropriately, we can engage stakeholders more meaningfully, foster stronger connections, and encourage active participation and

support. This approach also helps maintain consistency in communication while allowing flexibility to address diverse perspectives and priorities across communities.

5.1 Key Messages Overarching

Benefits of Circularity

make-a-thek inspires people to be creative with limited resources and technology.

We help people get active in their local circular economy.

We encourage them to move away from the design, use, and waste consumerism to consciously think about what they buy, make and use in fashion and crafts.

It is about the co-creation of attractive everyday alternatives. Buying second hand instead of new or repairing, reuse or resale instead of throwing away, quality instead of short-lived goods, renting instead of buying.

make-a-thek helps heritage craft skills be preserved, updated, shared and used as circular services.

We also inspire new circular business models and trial locally relevant circular products and services

Libraries as a community hub

It strengthens public libraries in being community hubs for local circular economies by providing knowledge, networks and infrastructure to crafts and fashion people.

We share our open source framework and the materials we develop so others can learn.

We co-create the make-a-thek initiative with selected libraries and local communities.

We bring together the great work that is already happening locally and give it an international platform for advocacy.

Accessibility, both financially and physically is important. We also focus on building individual's confidence and skills in making and crafting.

We discuss inclusivity as a core value and explore how libraries can become more welcoming, diverse, and empowering spaces for all members of the community.

We're piloting our model in European and international libraries

The first public library pilots will be launched in early 2026. The project is funded by the EU through its Horizon Europe programme for research and innovation and will run until January 2028.

5.2 Key Messages by Phase

In the communication implementation plan, we follow the project's communication campaign phases, which currently include: a **Pre-launch phase** (until mid-April 2025), a **Launch phase** (April 2025, during Fashion Revolution Week), a **Discovery phase** (focused on mapping and co-creation, running until around month 9 of the project), and a **Co-design phase** (overlapping with Discovery phase, starting in June 2025 and continuing until the opening of the pilot makerspaces). This will be followed by the **Pilot phase**, accompanying the operation of the makerspaces during Year 2, and finally the **Review and Upscale phase** in Year 3.

The phases in years 2 and 3 will be further refined and subdivided into more detailed stages as the project progresses.

In the graphic, the key messages for each phase are presented. The key messages for the phases in Year 2 and 3 may be adjusted as the project evolves:

Pre-Launch	Launch	Discovery	Co-Design	Pilots
<p>We are announcing the launch of the three-year EU Horizon project make-a-thek that started in February 2025 with nine partner organisations. The consortium partners met in person for a kick-off meeting in Brussels in mid-February.</p> <p>The consortium partners will share this announcement on their own organisational social media profiles, in their newsletters, and across their networks.</p>	<p>In April 2025, make-a-thek will be publicly launched during Fashion Revolution Week 2025 at an event in Berlin focused on the theme of "inclusive repair."</p> <p>The logo, corporate design, social media channels, and the first basic version of the website will be launched simultaneously.</p> <p>Newsletter sign-ups will begin on that day, with the first issue scheduled for release in May.</p>	<p>We're looking to connect with organisations, experts, and local communities who have experience in craft, circularity, and fashion. We want to understand what's needed to set up modular makerspaces in each of the public libraries we've chosen for our make-a-thek pilots.</p> <p>We will partner with several public libraries in Europe and Internationally to pilot make-a-thek.</p>	<p>For Libraries: We're engaging libraries through on-site or online meetings to explore the needs and interests of librarians and their communities regarding creative spaces in libraries.</p> <p>For Users: We invite makers, fashion designers, crafters, hobbyists, and curious individuals to share their ideas and preferences through a questionnaire to help shape creative spaces in their local libraries.</p>	<p>Our make-a-thek pilot makerspaces have started in 11 public libraries. A mobile library makerspace will travel through rural regions across Europe. This mobile tour will reach underrepresented communities.</p> <p>We welcome local businesses & communities to support our libraries to boost our facilities.</p>

Figure 09: overview of the first communication phases in the campaign

5.3 Timeline & Communication Phases

To ensure clear, effective, and targeted communication throughout the project, the communication campaign is divided into distinct phases. Each phase is guided by specific communication goals that reflect the project's progress and evolving focus. This phased structure, along with defined communication milestones, helps all stakeholders stay informed, maintain an overview, and align their efforts with the current priorities. The following visual outlines these phases and their corresponding key messages.

For each milestone PR announcement, FRG will take care of preparing and coordinating everything centrally. This includes creating a comprehensive kit with white label content for the announcement. The consortium partners and pilot libraries will mainly be responsible for sharing, forwarding, and—if relevant—contacting their own local networks and media. FRG will lead on international distribution and ensure consistent, professional outreach.

Figure 10: Timeline with communication phases & Milestone PR announcements

5.4 Responsibilities

FRG is leading Work Package 9 (WP 9) on CDO, working closely with the consortium to ensure effective coordination and maximize impact. Each partner organisation is asked to nominate a communication representative who will participate in regular meetings and serve as a liaison between the project team and their organisation's communications or marketing departments. Where needed, local partners will

translate project communications—originally produced in English—into their local languages.

To support this process, FRG recommends that each partner appoint a dedicated contact person responsible for CDO tasks within their organisation. This person will help generate make-a-thek-related content—such as website contributions—facilitate social media activity and partner networking, review communication materials, ensure accurate representation of the project at local events, and manage event promotion and reporting.

FRG will also coordinate overarching CDO efforts across the consortium, including reviewing local communication outputs and ensuring alignment with the project’s strategic goals.

Strong collaboration with all partners is essential to ensure the communication campaign strategy is both locally grounded and internationally effective. Each partner brings valuable expertise and influence within their respective sectors, contributing significantly to the project’s overall success.

5.4.1 Networks

make-a-thek plans to expand its impact by leveraging and connecting with key networks such as the New European Bauhaus, European Creative Hubs Network, TimeMachine, and others. By collaborating within these established communities, the project aims to ensure long-term economic, social, and political benefits while fostering effective cross-cultural communication. Consortium members will actively engage their networks to support needs assessment, content creation, piloting, scaling, and outreach, embedding make-a-thek activities into their ongoing work to guarantee sustainability.

The following Table shows how all consortium partners plan to utilise the reach of their network to scale the project impacts:

Table 06: overview of how CP use networks to scale project impact

CP	Network and Reach	Exploitation of make-a-thek
IAAC / Distributed Design Platform (DDP) / Fablab Barcelona	DDP reaches 60,000 people annually through its digital campaigns and actively promotes over 300 emerging creatives each year through its platform activities.	DDP’s outreach and community network will support open calls, events, and training, with its resources feeding into the Open Educational Resource (WP 5); IAAC will also build on make-a-thek outcomes in future projects.

<p>Fab City Foundation (FCF)</p>	<p>FCF links local ecosystems to global networks in 52 locations with 1,200+ members, complemented by the Fab Lab Network spanning 90+ countries and around 1,500 Fab Labs.</p>	<p>FCF will support make-a-thek through community access, knowledge exchange, and by integrating the project into its fullstack framework, aiding global pilots and long-term sustainability.</p>
<p>Global Innovation Gathering (GIG)</p>	<p>GIG is a global network of 180+ grassroots innovation hubs and makers across 47 countries, especially in the Global South, actively engaged in crafts and circularity, ready to collaborate, share knowledge, and scale impact through make-a-thek.</p>	<p>GIG will integrate make-a-thek results, including the KIT and OER, into its global open resource collection, enabling makerspaces worldwide to use and adapt them, while also forming a new community subgroup focused on circular craft and fashion.</p>
<p>Fashion Revolution Germany (FRG)</p>	<p>Fashion Revolution is a global movement active in over 90 countries, mobilising citizens, brands, and policymakers around fashion sustainability, with an annual campaign reaching over 569 million people and 700k engaged users.</p>	<p>2025 during Fashion Revolution Week, FRG will launch a global make-a-thek campaign with events across several countries, supported by a toolkit and online courses, while pilot outputs will be shared freely via their global website.</p>
<p>Ukrainian Makers Association (UMA)</p>	<p>UMA engages make-a-thek target groups through events and a network of 17 hubs and 2400 makers, and collaborates with the Ukrainian Libraries Association to establish makerspaces in libraries.</p>	<p>Through UMA, make-a-thek supports Ukraine's rebuilding by empowering local makerspaces with pilots, networking, shared knowledge, funding opportunities, and promotional tools to strengthen community resilience.</p>
<p>Public Libraries 2030 (PL2030)</p>	<p>PL2030 is a network of over 50 innovative European public libraries that collaborates with its members and partners closely with EBLIDA, the European library association umbrella organization.</p>	<p>PL2030's communication channels and events engage key European library stakeholders, with a strong focus on circularity and co-learning, aiming to expand makerspaces inspired by the make-a-thek approach and support its long-term replication in public libraries.</p>
<p>European Crafts Alliance (ECA)</p>	<p>ECA is a European network of 37 craft organizations from 22 countries, representing thousands of craft professionals, with a mission</p>	<p>ECA will engage local craft stakeholders, promote the project through its media and events, and integrate the knowledge gained into future</p>

	to promote crafts as vital to Europe’s cultural, social, and economic well-being.	activities.
Centre for Social Innovation - ZSI	ZSI is a private research institution, closely connected to networks of Social Innovation and Citizen Science (e.g. ECSA, the European Citizen Science Association)	ZSI will explore the societal readiness of make-a-thek and communicate findings in their networks; it will also highlight the participatory elements of make-a-thek in the Citizen Science community.

6. CDO Implementation

6.1 Communications Campaign Implementation Plan

A communications campaign implementation plan is essential for translating a project's communication campaign strategy into concrete, actionable steps. It ensures that key messages reach the right audiences at the right time, through appropriate channels. The communication implementation plan is a practical roadmap that turns strategic intentions into day-to-day communication activities, helping a project to stay on track, stay visible, and connect meaningfully with its audiences.

The communications plan is aligned with the defined communication phases and key milestones.

It is accessible to all CP, and participation in contributing upcoming content is encouraged. Depending on the scale of the planned event or content, FRG holds individual meetings with the involved partners in advance to define targeted communication goals, discuss how these goals can best be achieved, and identify the concrete actions required. The plan is maintained by FRG and updated daily or at least once a week.

make-a-thek communication plan

Public launch of the project

Date	What	Audience	Channel external	Channel internal	Purpose	Key messages	Responsible & deadlines	Status
05.04.2025	Event announcement by event partner	librarians fashion industry politicians circular economy experts media craftspeople Project stakeholders local press social media	Instagram Facebook event		Announcement from event organisers to show credibility - find out if press are invited.	Targeted towards music	Sema -	done
05.04.2025	FRG announce event	librarians fashion industry politicians circular economy experts media craftspeople Project stakeholders local press social media	Instagram Facebook		Supporting event announcement and engage with our network - activation (journalists, political people)	Be a part of the revolution - promote FRG newsletter and social media channels. CTA is follow us on social media	Hanna	done
23.04.2025	share website & Social accounts with partners	Project stakeholders		Basecamp	publish LP & Social accounts and share with partners	This is our temporary landing page & Social accounts. Have a look and share in your networks	23.4. Hanna	done
23.04.2025	share Social Media Plan with partners	Project stakeholders		Basecamp	share the social media plan to get insight into planned posts		23.4. Hanna	done
23.04.2025	White label content to partners about make-a-thek	Project stakeholders		Basecamp	share the launch	Its FRW and we are thrilled to launch make-a-thek on our event on 24.4. in Berlin, etc...	23.4. Hanna	done
23.04.2025	Find and contact a group of journalists to follow our journey	circular economy experts fashion industry	Email		Identify key existing contacts who would be interested and get in touch with first news on make-a-thek		18.4. Carina	done
24.04.2025	Comms Campaign kick-off	librarians fashion industry circular economy experts local press	Facebook Instagram Linked in Email website		On Fashion Revolution Day we kick of the comms campaign on Social channels (insta, FB, LinkedIn) and post our first posts, share the website and CTA to follow social accounts & newsletter		Hanna 18.4.	done
24.04.2025	Infobooth - mat representation on Glaspalast FRW event	craftspeople media circular economy experts fashion industry librarians local press	event Instagram		meet stakeholders and present the mat project and goals		Hanna & Cari	done
24.04.2025	Paneltalk - mat representation on Glaspalast FRW event	craftspeople media circular economy experts fashion industry librarians local press	event Instagram		Max will be speaking in the panel about inclusive repairing & present mat on the event		FRG mat team / Max	done
25.04.2025	Tracking Sheet Posts	Project stakeholders		Basecamp	track shared content	asking our partners every 2-4 weeks to update the sheet	11.4. Hanna	done

Timeline - Pre-Launch - Launch apr 25 - Discovery CA & events may - dec 25 - Design of Pilots jun - dec 25 - Pilots - Review & Share - NEB festival

Figure 11: Screenshot of the spreadsheet “communication plan”

6.2 Digital Implementation

6.2.1 Website

The website runs under the URL **makeathek.eu**.

The make-a-thek website serves as the project’s central online platform, playing a crucial role in visibility, communication, and knowledge sharing. Its development, content generation, ongoing maintenance, and management are essential project activities.

The website provides a structured and accessible hub for:

- General information about the project, its goals, and vision
- Profiles and overviews of all consortium partner organisations
- Access to open-source resources and tools developed throughout the project, including:
 - Communication Toolkit
 - OER (will be linked as soon as the WP finishes the OER)
 - Makerspace Toolkit (will be linked as soon as the WP finishes the OER)

- A regularly updated calendar of project events
- Latest news and updates
- Public deliverables and results
- Press area, including press releases and a downloadable press kit
- Newsletter subscription
- Contact details and project address
- Direct links to related networks and communities such as Distributed Design Platform, JustFashionEU, or CircularBerlin
- White-label integration options for partner websites
- Proper attribution to the European Union’s Horizon Framework Programme, including necessary disclaimers regarding European Commission responsibility

This platform ensures transparency, open access, and engagement for a wide range of stakeholders.

To maximise online visibility and engagement with key stakeholders, the design and content strategy of the website are carefully developed. FRG has taken a user-centred and technically robust approach, ensuring that both functionality and accessibility are aligned with project goals.

Key design and technical considerations include:

- User Experience (UX) & User Interface (UI) Design: A high-quality UX/UI approach ensures intuitive navigation and a smooth user journey throughout the site.
- Responsive Design: The website is fully responsive, adapting to various devices such as smartphones, tablets, and desktops to maintain a consistent and high-quality display of images and content.
- Interconnectivity: Back-links, embedded links, and sub-domains are used to connect the main make-a-thek website seamlessly with other related platforms developed within the project.
- Cross-Platform Promotion: Content is structured to allow for easy sharing and discoverability across social media and partner platforms, strengthening outreach and visibility.
- Search Engine Optimization (SEO): Keyword optimization is implemented to improve searchability in Google and other engines. Target keywords include “makerspace,” “public libraries,” “social innovation,” “heritage crafts” “circular economy” and “fashion”.
- Clear Content Structure: Logical page hierarchies, clear titles, and concise copy enhance both SEO performance and the overall user experience.
- Legal Compliance: The website includes a legal disclaimer aligned with GDPR regulations. This also applies to the e-newsletter sign-up process.

Together, these elements ensure the make-a-thek website functions as an accessible, engaging, and effective communication tool for a wide audience.

6.2.2 Newsletter

FRG has already established a quarterly e-newsletter using the third-party platform Mailchimp, which ensures GDPR-compliant handling of personal data. The newsletter shares updates on project progress, upcoming events, and key developments.

In addition to the dedicated make-a-thek newsletter, project updates are also communicated through existing mailing lists managed by consortium members and affiliated partners to broaden outreach and engagement. The link to sign up for the newsletter is: <http://eepurl.com/jcQ0pl>

6.2.3 Social Media

The primary goal of make-a-thek's social media presence is to raise awareness about the project and encourage active participation in future make-e-thek makerspaces. FRG will manage the social media channels to create engaging content that sparks interest and motivates audiences to get involved. By using a consistent project handle and hashtag— #makeathek #makerspacesinlibraries — across all platforms, the project aims to build a recognizable online identity. FRG will facilitate interaction with project partners, who are also expected to promote the project by tagging the handle and hashtag in their posts. A shared Google Drive file keeps track of all partners' social media accounts to coordinate efforts effectively.

Instagram

@makeathek is the project name on Instagram

Instagram posts provide visually engaging updates and event information about the project. Collaborating with other WPs to gather content, FRG utilises media like images and videos to captivate and involve stakeholders on Instagram.

LinkedIn

@make-a-hek is the project name on LinkedIn

LinkedIn showcases the project's professional aspect, targeting industry, policy makers, and circularity professionals. The make-a-thek LinkedIn page shares updates, events, and project results. FRG actively connects with project partners and experts relevant to the make-a-thek fields.

Facebook

@Make-a-thek is the project name on Facebook.

A Facebook page is created for visibility on the platform. The Facebook page shares project events, updates, and outputs. In year two of the project, Facebook is used more intensively to reach targeted communities through Facebook groups.

YouTube

The creation of a YouTube channel is currently under consideration for year 2 of the project. This channel would support coverage of the ongoing pilot makerspaces

and, in particular, the planned mobile makerspace. It is expected to be developed between months 7 and 12 of the project timeline.

Other Channels

TikTok will be used in the second year to engage the community, but initially not through an own make-a-thek channel. A dedicated channel will only be launched once there is enough original video content and the effort to maintain daily posts is justified and meaningful. In the meantime, or as an alternative, TikTok channels of consortium partners will be used to achieve more efficient outreach.

6.3 Offline Strategy & Merch Materials

6.3.1 Digital and Print Posters and Templates

In line with the project’s Visual Guidelines, FRG has developed a range of informative print and digital materials to promote the project. These resources, available in the communications toolkit, include: Social media banners and posts, event posters, printed flyers and bookmarks, branded sewing sets.

Figure 12: make-a-thek flyers, sewing sets, bookmarks and posters

PCP also developed some interactive, make-a-thek-branded tools — like the Strings Map — designed to be used at events, workshops, and co-creation sessions. They help spark engagement with participants and offer a fun way to explore and identify the needs of the community.

Figure 13: Interactive Strings Map

6.3.2 Project Presentation

An overview of the project and its expected impact to be used by the project partners for presentations about the project, events and conferences. This presentation will be updated regularly depending on the project status.

6.4 Events

Events play a central role in the successful implementation of the make-a-thek communication campaign within the CDO strategy. They offer valuable opportunities to engage with key stakeholders and politicians.

Three main types of events are foreseen:

- Events organised and delivered by make-a-thek consortium members
- External events attended by consortium members
- Events where make-a-thek is invited to participate or present the project

make-a-thek will be represented across various formats and scales, including Community Meetups, Knowledge Exchange Webinars, Matchmaking Events, as well as international conferences, congresses, workshops, exhibitions, and fairs.

All project partners are expected to participate in events relevant to their sector.

FRG will provide a make-a-thek events kit—available in the Communications Toolkit—including project presentation and merch materials. When partners plan to

attend an event, they must inform FRG with all relevant details so the participation can be promoted on the project website and social media.

Partners are required to use the official events kit and ensure visibility of the make-a-thek logo and EU Horizon funding acknowledgment. A list of anticipated events can be seen in the following table and will be updated throughout the project.

Table 07: List of planned events (to be updated throughout the project)

Name of Event	Purpose
New European Bauhaus Festival (NEB)	The NEB Festival unites people worldwide to explore and promote a sustainable, beautiful, and inclusive future. make-a-thek can participate by organizing events and activities within the festival's various formats to engage the public with the project's goals and results.
Fashion Revolution Week (FRW)	Fashion Revolution Week will launch the make-a-thek communication campaign, highlighting craft communities in fashion. FR city ambassadors will promote make-a-thek in local libraries. The 2026 German campaign will focus on libraries and fashion SMEs, with the toolkit shared across Europe. Additional FR events will occur throughout the project.
Berlin Fashion Week (BFW)	During Berlin Fashion Week, make-a-thek may participate in events like 202030 – The Berlin Fashion Summit, which focuses on fashion sustainability and the EU Textile Strategy.
Milan Design Week + Brera Design days	Milano Design Week (April) and Brera Design Days (September) are annual Milan events showcasing design innovations and offer key opportunities to present circular projects and professionals from the piloting and scaling phases.
Maker Faire Rome	Maker Faire Rome, Europe's largest Maker Faire, collaborates with OD and offers make-a-thek a chance to present the make-a-kit and showcase circular solutions using digital fabrication from the piloting and scaling phases.
Global Innovation Gathering Weekend and re:publica	Since 2013, GIG hosts a summit and pop-up makerspace at re:publica, one of the most important digital society events worldwide happening each year in Berlin/Germany and will include make-a-thek activities like workshops and talks.
Distributed Design	The Distributed Design Conference unites global innovators and designers to share trends and ideas,

Platform Conference	providing a unique platform for make-a-thek community engagement and dissemination.
NEXT Library festival	NEXT Library is a bi-annual international conference for innovative library professionals, with upcoming editions in 2026 and 2028 where PL2030 will showcase make-a-thek in an interactive session.
International Mobile Library Congress	The International Mobile Library Congress, organized by the German library association, gathers over 30 mobile libraries from across Europe and will be integrated into the make-a-thek bus tour.
Fashion Revolution Community Events	Fashion Revolution offices in Belgium, Croatia, Italy, Ukraine, Slovenia, and Portugal will host local events like clothing swaps, workshops, bootcamps, and policy dialogues, while Berlin's Circular.Berlin organizes circularity roundtables to engage the local community.
World Circular Economy Forum (WCEF)	The WCEF, organized by the Finnish Innovation Fund Sitra, is a global platform promoting circular economy principles and offers a valuable opportunity to showcase the results of make-a-thek pilots.

6.5 Press

The project will gain visibility through various media channels, including online blogs, magazines, and the websites of other projects funded under the same call or by major funding bodies. To maximise outreach, FRG will develop press releases highlighting key milestones, events, deliverables, or other newsworthy outputs of public or industry relevance. These will be shared with targeted media contacts as needed.

Within the WP9 a press distribution list is set up with over 150 international media contacts to ensure broad coverage in the fashion-, crafts-, maker- and circular economy branches. Additionally, a growing database of media and press contacts will be maintained throughout the project.

Project partners—and any interested media outlets—are encouraged to distribute these press releases through their own channels and translate them into local languages where appropriate. Each organisation's designated communication representative will manage this process.

The communication team will actively monitor media coverage and collect press clippings to track the project's visibility and impact.

6.6 Dissemination and Communication Policy and Rules

The support of the EU for the make-a-thek project must be prominently acknowledged on all CDO materials, tools, and communication channels. This is achieved by including the following disclaimer:

The EU logo will be featured on all project materials. Additionally, scientific and research publications must include the following statement:

“Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Commission. Neither the European Union nor the European Commission can be held responsible for them.”

The make-a-thek logo should also be prominently displayed on all CDO materials and project outputs. It is available along with the Communications Toolkit.

Project partners are expected to provide their logos for inclusion on the project website and relevant CDO outputs. They should also showcase their involvement in make-a-thek on their own organisation’s website by incorporating the logo, linking to the main make-a-thek website, and including a brief project description.

7. Monitoring and Evaluation

7.1. Monitoring

The CDO tasks will be carried out by the entire make-a-thek consortium, with FRG responsible for regular monitoring. A combination of qualitative and quantitative methods will be used to assess progress, with key metrics tracked in a shared Google Drive spreadsheet to evaluate audience reach and stakeholder engagement.

FRG will stay up to date on partner activities through regular meetings and will follow up directly in the case of special events or initiatives. This ongoing monitoring will help evaluate the effectiveness of CDO tools and actions. The strategy may be updated as needed to ensure continued impact and success throughout the project.

Website Analytics

- Number of visitors, Number of page views
- Monitored using Google analytics and Analytics on Squarespace

Social Media Analytics

- Average post impressions, number of account followers

- Monitored using app-based analytics tool
- Social Media Posts by make-a-thek accounts and CP accounts will be tracked in a monitoring list on Google Drive

Press Clipping

- Publications in major media outlets with high reach or relevance to the project’s target audiences will be documented and archived through media clippings.

Events

- Forthcoming submission and application opportunities
- Consortium-wide event planning will ensure consistent local activities and a coordinated programme of workshops across Europe
- The event location, type and amount of attendees will be tracked in a list on Google Drive

7.2 Evaluation

FRG is responsible for continuously assessing the effectiveness of the communication campaign and dissemination strategy. The following targets will serve as benchmarks for evaluating progress in Communication, Dissemination, and Outreach activities.

Table 08: Key performance Indicators for evaluation

Website	30.000 visits during the whole project > 50 organisations using communication campaign toolkit and assets (WP 8,9&10)
Social Media	> 900 new social media followers across all participating partners (WP 9&10) > 300 original #makeathek posts and 1.200 external or re-posts (related to activities & events) (WP 9&10)
Press	> 6 Press Releases and at least 30 press articles with media coverage across all project activities (WP9&10)
Events	> 12 community meetups with at least 400 people participating in networking activities (WP 6,8,9&10) in total.

	> 12 promotional events including press conferences and launch events for pilots (WP 9&10)
Educational Resources	1000 unique users viewing or downloading the KIT, OER or Guide (WP 9&10)

8. Summary

To ensure broad visibility and impact of the make-a-thek project beyond the consortium, this Communication, Dissemination, and Outreach (CDO) plan has been designed to support efficient and effective implementation. It will be regularly used by the consortium, under the coordination of FRG, and made available on Google Drive as a living document that will be updated as needed.

Annex

make-a-thek Styleguide

BRAND & COMMUNICATION GUIDELINES
– OPEN SOURCE JULY 2025 –

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PREAMBLE

Welcome to the make-a-thek styleguide. Here you'll find helpful tips on how to use make-a-thek's communication assets and tools.

Due to the co-creative process of make-a-thek, communication may need to be adapted slightly over the course of the project.

This Styleguide is shared open source and can be used by every library, makerspace, organisation, brand etc, that wants to work on projects to support circular co-creation around the topics of public libraries, fashion, crafts, makers.

The collection of graphics and illustrations can grow over time, depending on the requirements and changes to the project.

COMMS & BRAND GUIDELINES TIMETABLE

2025

2026

April 25
• BETA Version
(completed)

July 25
• **RELEASE**
Version

future
• extensions &
minimal
adjustments

RESPONSIBILITIES

make-a-thek is represented by 9 consortium members from European countries.

Fashion Revolution Germany (FRG) is one of them and responsible for communication, dissemination & outreach of make-a-thek.

If you need support regarding communications, please get in touch with FRG (hanna.gebauer@future.fashion).

ZENTRUM FÜR SOZIALE INNOVATION
CENTRE FOR SOCIAL INNOVATION

QUESTIONS ON COMMS?

ASK FASHION REVOLUTION GERMANY

**FASHION
REVOLUTION
GERMANY**

NAME

make-a-thek

make-a-thek is a proper noun and is always written in lower case, whether at the beginning or in the middle of a sentence.

Always write make-a-thek with hyphens.

mat

When using the acronym mat, make sure you put this in brackets first.

Example: make-a-thek (mat).

Don't get confused: our URL, social media handles, hashtag, and even our logo are all written without hyphens – simple and easy to remember.

make
a
thek

-tone of voice

make-a-thek uses clear, concrete language because it is an inclusive brand that is active both locally and internationally. Although it is a fun brand, we don't play with meaning. We make it easy to understand.

Sentences are short and easily translatable. We use modern, clean headings. Body text is just the right length to say what it needs to say.

The colourful, creative and artistic part of the brand is expressed through inspiring visuals and activating content formats.

We base our communication on the values of the New European Bauhaus: inclusive, sustainable, and beautiful.

EASY

CLEAR

FUN

CONSISTENT

VISION

make-a-thek envisions public libraries as a place for circular economy experience and co-creation focused on fashion and crafts.

MISSION

make-a-thek pilots a scalable co-creation model with selected European and international public libraries, building on existing community networks and initiatives.

MAKE-A-THEK CORE STORY

In a disconnected world of fast fashion and throw-away things, make-a-thek brings back creativity, craftship and community. By partnering with selected libraries in Europe and beyond, make-a-thek gives a place for innovation, learning and sharing, promoting a more circular, local economy.

It brings together the great work that is already happening; strengthens public libraries as community hubs, and offers an international platform for the community circular movement.

We encourage people to move away from the consumerism model of design, use and waste to consciously thinking about what they buy, make, and use in fashion and crafts. We also inspire new circular business models by co-creating

the needed infrastructure for local production, care, repair and reuse or recycling. This allows for locally meaningful circular products and services to be trialled in a real-life setting.

make-a-thek pilots at selected public libraries and will be launched in early 2026. We will be transparent about our project. We'll share our open source framework and resources so others can learn.

make-a-thek is funded by the European Union through its Horizon Europe program for research and innovation. make-a-thek will run until January 2028.

SLOGANS

Where Public Libraries Inspire Circular Co-Creation.

Connecting Communities for Circular Fashion and Crafts.

Co-Creating Circular Futures in Public Libraries.

DESCRIPTION OF PROJECT

What is make-a-thek?

make-a-thek is an EU funded project that brings modular, easy-to-replicate makerspaces into public libraries. These spaces focus on fashion and crafts, offering open access to innovative and circular approaches to making and design.

Through community co-creation, the project will develop a practical toolkit and free educational resources (OERs) to help libraries set up their own fashion- and craft-focused makerspaces.

The project will pilot these ideas in at least 12 libraries (9 in Europe, 3 internationally), where communities will explore how to combine traditional heritage crafts with modern digital tools like 3D printing and laser cutting. This approach supports sharing sustainable skills and cultural knowledge.

Rooted in New European Bauhaus values:

Inclusivity – opening access to creative technologies and inviting communities to shape the green transition.

Sustainability – encouraging hands-on participation in building a circular society.

Enrichment – enabling personal and shared creativity through fashion and crafts.

Long-term goals:

- Empower a new generation of prosumers—people who both create and use in sustainable ways.
- Position libraries as hubs for circular making and knowledge-sharing.
- Preserve heritage crafts through digital innovation.
- Foster circular and green innovation in fashion and crafts.

To ensure lasting impact, make-a-thek will also create a scaling guide to help libraries and cultural institutions adopt and spread this approach widely.

COMMUNICATION CHANNELS

- Website
 - <https://www.makeathek.eu/>
- Email Newsletter [sign up here](#)
- Social Media
 - Instagram [@makeathek](#)
 - Facebook [@makeathek](#)
 - LinkedIn [@makeathek](#)
- Press
 - Local press
 - Industry press
 - International press
- Other “White Label”
 - We provide content for other newsletters/ social media
- Events

HASHTAGS

Using hashtags is important for measuring impact and reach.

Please always include the English hashtags for your posts to be measured as part of our international impact.

You can include additional hashtags in your own language too.

Please use these hashtag in your posts:

#makeathek

#HorizonEU

#EUInnovation

#CircularSpaceInMyLibrary

#MakeFashionCraftsCircular

#CoCreateCommunity

#LibrariesOfTomorrow

#NewEuropeanBauhaus

#ResearchImpactEU

LOGO

The make-a-thek logo is available in different versions.

The **main logo** should always be the first choice.

The **mat icon** is used when the main logo is no longer legible at smaller scales..

Download the logo [here](#) or find it in the brand kit in Canva.

PRIMARY
main logo

SECONDARY
mat icon

LOGO

The black & white version of the main logo & icon can always be used alternatively.

The contrast to the background must be clear to ensure good legibility.

good contrast:

too little contrast:

main logo

secondary - mat icon

LOGO

To keep it modular and fun, additional colour versions of the logo and icon can be used.

The contrast to the background must be clear to ensure good legibility.

The elemental logo can be used when a very clear visual language is the better fit.

main logo

secondary - mat icon

secondary - elemental logo

LOGO

This page shows the ways to use the logo or any variant when the deliverable is a professional project such as letter heads, printed files, etc.

Always use the logo in its original form. Do not alter, stretch, or change its colours.

Legibility is key on professional documents so do not exceed minimum sizing and ensure adequate spacing is given. Also avoid overlaying or turning the logo.

avoid turning

don't cover or overlay

TYPOGRAPHY

“Work Sans” is a clean and modern font with a simple, geometric style and a touch of warmth. It’s designed to be easy to read on screens, making it ideal for websites, apps, branding, and editorial design.

Download the font [here](#) or find them in the brand kit in Canva.

mat

Headings
Work Sans - Black

**ABCDEFGHIJKLM
NOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklm
nopqrstuvwxyz**

**0123456789
!%&+ -= ()/**

Subheadings
Work Sans - Bold

**ABCDEFGHIJKLM
NOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklm
nopqrstuvwxyz**

**0123456789
!%&+ -= ()/**

Body Copy
Work Sans - Regular

ABCDEFGHIJKLM
NOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklm
nopqrstuvwxyz

0123456789
!%&+ -= ()/

TYPOGRAPHY

This page shows how to use the core fonts.

Only use the core fonts and colours from the palette.

Legibility is key on professional documents so stick to at least 10pt for main text.

Subheadings can sit between headings and secondary copy.

Headings in Work Sans - Black

Subheadings in Work Sans - Bold

Secondary & body copy in
Work Sans - Regular

SECONDARY & SUBHEADINGS
IN WORK SANS - REGULAR -
CAPITAL LETTERS

COLOUR

This is the make-a-thek colour palette. These colours can all be used as they are shown here or as a tint.

The brightest versions are mainly intended for use in larger formats or in areas where they will be prominently displayed. The strong colours are used as primary colours.

GRADIENTS

Colour gradients can be created in linear or radial patterns from the entire gradients palette shown here.

Colour gradients can be used as backgrounds, as fillers for shapes or as a creative stylistic device.

Download them [here](#) or find them in the brand kit in Canva.

#eba369 - #3d46e6

#dddddd - #d2r0ff

#e8dcfa - #d2r0ff

#ebfdde - #293381

#ebfdde - #d1b2f8

#ebeae1 - #ffcfc7

#ffe391 - #d1b2f8

#ababab - #eba369

#8ad861 - #8141ff

GRAPHIC ELEMENTS

Our graphic visual language is based on simple geometric shapes and simple organic forms.

In combination with this, there are hand-drawn illustrations that can be added just like the icons.

Don't use too many playful graphic elements at once, less is more :)

Download them [here](#) or find them in the brand kit in Canva.

make-a-thek logo form

organic form

geometric form

illustrations

ICONS

Our Icons can be used for illustrative purposes or as pictograms. Download them [here](#).

circularity/closed loop

fashion

open source

crafts

inclusiveness

local

participate

digital innovation

knowledge

network

IMAGES & VIDEOS

Find our make-a-thek stock photos here [Link](#)

Due to the complexity of make-a-thek, we want to show versatility with our photos and not give strict guidelines for the visual language of photos and videos being created by participants or by the consortium, except that they are based on the values of the project: beautiful, versatile, diverse, inspiring, inclusive, co-creative, fun.

Nonetheless, a few suggestions:

- Pay attention to image rights and ask people for permission. (Could you alternatively show details of hands in the processes of making, crafting, repairing, etc?)
- Don't take pictures against the light unless you want to create a certain mood.
- Photograph and film upright for social media.
- If you want to show pictures digitally (e.g. on social media), edit the pictures a little brighter and with a slightly higher contrast to give them a little spice.
- Add picture descriptions to pictures and give credits.

#makeathek makeathek.eu @makeathek

**Funded by
the European Union**